

Integrating Mission and System Analyses in the BANTER Project for Nuclear Bimodal Propulsion

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Abstract

Since the 1950s, nuclear reactors have been considered for both thermonuclear and nuclear-electric space propulsion. Recent concepts explore bimodal systems, combining these two propulsion types within a shared nuclear reactor. The EU-funded project Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket (BANTER) introduces a novel approach by employing ammonia as a common propellant for both propulsion types. Ammonia, with its high hydrogen content and non-cryogenic storage capabilities, presents a viable alternative to hydrogen, especially given the recent ammonia resource discoveries on Moon and Mars. Within BANTER, ammonia serves a triple function: as propellant for thermonuclear propulsion, as working fluid for an open asynchronous Brayton cycle, and as propellant for electric propulsion. This integrated approach supports a compact, high-performance propulsion system deployable in orbit with a single launch, enabling long operational lifetimes, multiple trips, and enhanced manoeuvrability for deep-space missions. To assess the feasibility and efficiency of this bimodal concept, comprehensive mission and system analyses are essential. These studies evaluate the impact of integrating high-power electric propulsion into the spacecraft design, optimizing system performance, and ensuring compatibility with long-duration space transportation requirements. The BANTER concept integrates multiple subsystems, including propellant management, electric thrusters, and power generation. For high-thrust manoeuvres, the nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) system leverages reactor-generated heat to dissociate and expand ammonia, providing the necessary thrust for rapid orbital transfers and deep-space missions supported by the reduced molar mass. However, the nuclear reactor must also continuously generate electrical power throughout the mission, enabling the operation of electric thrusters using ammonia as propellant. The mission analysis defines a detailed target mission, incorporating hybrid manoeuvres and including orbital characteristics and propulsion system operational modes. The system is designed to facilitate interplanetary exploration, Earth-Moon-Mars cargo transport, and deep-space operations. The mission analyses provide a detailed assessment of a target mission using standard aerodynamics tools, leading to the development of a comprehensive requirements list at both system and subsystem levels. During the first phase mission analyses of the BANTER project purely nuclear electric propulsion (NEP) driven transfers have been assessed, for which results are given in this paper. These analyses rely on analytical methods using the dimensionless form of Tsiolkovsky equation for optimizing the payload mass fraction and obtaining required thruster parameters. These results will be later compared to transfers conducted by purely NTP systems and hybrid transfers using NTP for high-thrust and NEP for high specific impulse manoeuvres.

Keywords: Bimodal propulsion, nuclear thermal propulsion, nuclear electric propulsion, mission analyses, system analyses, dimensionless Tsiolkovsky equation

Nomenclature

Δv	Velocity increment, m/s
F	Thrust, N
γ	Gravitational constant, $6.674 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{s}^2)$
g_0	Standard gravitational acceleration, 9.81 m/s^2
h_{NSO}	Altitude of Nuclear Safe Orbit, m
I_{sp}	Specific impulse, s
μ_{pl}	Payload mass fraction, -
μ_{pls}	Payload-structure mass fraction, -

μ_{prop}	Propellant mass fraction, -
μ_{PS}	Propulsion system mass fraction, -
μ_S	Structure mass fraction, -
M	Mass of reference planet, kg
m_{PS}	Mass of propulsion system, kg
η_T	Thrust efficiency, -
P_{el}	Electrical power for EPS, W
r	Orbit radius, m
τ	Transfer time, s
$\tau_{1/2}$	Transfer time of outbound/return flight, s
v	Spacecraft velocity, m/s
v_c	Energy characteristic velocity, m/s

Acronyms/Abbreviations

BANTER	Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket
EPS	Electric Propulsion System
ESA	European Space Agency
LLO	Low Lunar Orbit
LMO	Low Martian Orbit
MATLAB	Matrix Laboratory
MPDT	Magnetoplasmadynamic Thruster
NEP	Nuclear Electric Propulsion
NSO	Nuclear Safe Orbit
NTP	Nuclear Thermal Propulsion
PGS	Power Generation System
PMS	Propellant Management System
RCS	Attitude Control System
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

1. Motivation

The area of space exploration stands at the threshold of a revolutionary leap, driven by innovative nuclear and propulsion technologies that hold the potential for unprecedented space missions. For deep space missions with destinations such as the cis-lunar region, Mars, and beyond the distance to the Sun influences the available solar power, affecting the viability of photovoltaic systems and enabling nuclear energy systems. Additionally, analyses of staged launchers and their achieved velocity increment Δv reveal the necessity of advanced propulsion systems, i.e. electric propulsion systems (EPS), for complex missions. Higher thrust densities of propulsion systems address low thrust issues of EPSs enabling reduced propellant mass and increased payload mass fractions for deep space missions.

Nuclear electric propulsion (NEP) shows significant potential as an innovative propulsion model, primarily due to its utilization of a nuclear-based power source capable of providing both high specific impulse and substantial thrust levels within an EPS. Thermal power, generated by a nuclear reactor, heats a working fluid of a thermodynamic cycle to generate electrical power for an EPS. Independent from the distance to the Sun as well as shadows cast by celestial bodies, it addresses a critical need for efficient, large-scale transportation from Earth orbits and the cis-lunar region to destinations as Mars and beyond. The combination of obtaining high specific impulse (high propellant efficiency) on the one hand and high thrust levels (short manoeuvre/transfer time) on the other hand is pivotal in overcoming

the inherent challenges associated with interplanetary travel, offering a viable solution for missions requiring extended durations and significant payloads.

Nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP), on the other hand, offers the potential to provide performance double that of the best chemical thrusters along with thrust levels necessary for human exploration or mass scales associated with significant scientific spacecrafts [1]. In NTP systems, propellant is raised to high pressure in a turbopump assembly, passed through a high-power reactor, where it is heated to significant temperatures, and exhausted through a nozzle at high velocities for thrust generation. The propellant should ideally feature a low molecular mass to increase the systems specific impulse [2]. NTP enables human exploration on Mars and has the potential to revolutionize the scientific exploration of the solar system's outer planets. While NTP systems offer comparable high thrust-to-weight levels, NEP benefits with significant increased specific impulses leading to lower propellant consumptions and consequently higher payload mass fractions.

In more recent years, bimodal nuclear propulsion systems have been proposed, referring to the fact that two propulsion systems (in this case NTP and NEP systems) sharing an element, namely the nuclear reactor, may offer advantages in terms of exploration opportunities and overall system masses. A nuclear propulsion system combined of turbopumps and a nozzle for NTP, as well as a power generation system (PGS) and high-power electric thrusters for NEP, may be capable of providing high thrust levels or high specific impulses, where needed during a space mission. While the two propulsion systems, proposed in the literature for bimodal nuclear systems, do not share the same propellant, the BANTER (Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket) project proposes the first system in which the same propellant is used for both thermonuclear and electric propulsion [3]. The aim of BANTER is to design a bimodal propulsion system using ammonia as propellant for the nuclear thermal thruster, the electric thrusters of the NEP subsystem, and as working fluid for the PGS.

The paper starts with an overview of the BANTER project including the project's main idea, the objectives, and the description of its subsystems. This work describes the mission and system analyses conducted during the first project phase of BANTER, focussing on analyses for the NEP system. By applying analytical methods with the dimensionless Tsiolkovsky equation it is possible to obtain mission and system requirements like mission duration, required specific impulses, and thrust efficiencies. Single transfer and space tug missions to Moon and Mars are assessed in the BANTER project. The results of these primary analyses are presented, along with an outlook on further methodologies for processing these results and integrating them into the overall BANTER system.

2. The BANTER Project

BANTER is a project funded by the European Union under the European Innovation Council grant agreement No. 101186520 and conducted by a consortium of University of Pisa, University of Stuttgart, Centrum Vyzkumu Rez Sro, and Novaspaces. The main idea of BANTER is to design a compact bimodal propulsion system capable of being placed in orbit with a single launch, which can transport tons of payload to the most attractive destinations of the solar system. Thus, transfers to Moon and Mars are assessed considering a system's high operational life to carry out multiple trips, and with high performance allowing great versatility in the manoeuvres to be carried out. In the BANTER project, ammonia is used as propellant for the NTP and NEP system, the latter including ammonia as propellant for the electric thrusters, as well as working fluid for the PGS. The project objectives to demonstrate the proof-of-principle of this game-changing technology involve the following steps:

- * Definition of BANTER reference system/subsystem requirements.
- * Design and analysis of an innovative nuclear fission reactor for a bimodal propulsion system.
- * Design of an innovative electric power generation cycle for a bimodal propulsion system using ammonia as working fluid.
- * Development and testing of two lab-scale systems for NTP and one for NEP.

Two coolant channel prototypes will demonstrate the ammonia decomposition and verify the subsequent increase in performance while an ammonia fed electric thruster will evaluate the performance in the low-thrust range of the proposed bimodal propulsion system. Ammonia allows the development of a compact propulsion system capable of transporting tons of payloads for a wide spectrum of missions due to its ease of storage in non-cryogenic conditions, compared to the usually favoured propellant hydrogen for NTP. The presence of ammonia as an in-situ resource on many targets of future space missions and its possibility of decomposing to increase the propulsive performance are further benefits for using it as shared propellant. Interplanetary transport missions to Moon and Mars are favoured with the BANTER system according to the discovery of ammonia resources on these celestial bodies [4] and Europe's major interests for the coming decades: interplanetary exploration, Earth-Moon-Mars cargo, and deep-space missions [5].

Nevertheless, the reference missions for the entire project involve transporting several cargoes in multiple trips between the so-called Nuclear Safe Orbit (NSO) and low lunar or Martian orbits. The goal of the project's system analyses is to offer a propulsion system that combines reduced costs with high performance. This will enable Europe to capture a share of the mission market where hydrogen-based systems are too complex and expensive, and chemical propulsion systems lack sufficient performance. The BANTER project will impact the European space industry by the possibility of greatly reducing the system development and launch costs with ammonia instead of hydrogen as propellant, as well as providing superior performance to any chemical propulsion system.

In particular, for lunar missions, the system proposed by BANTER offers several strategic advantages. It can be quickly inserted into orbit and is immediately ready for use. Thanks to the potential for in-situ resource utilization of ammonia on the Moon, the system will be capable of performing multiple trips between NSO and lunar orbits. By enabling rapid transport of essential cargo, it may significantly accelerate the development of human outposts on the Moon. Additionally, the system may serve as a cargo ship for the Lunar Gateway, offering critical logistical support for a wide range of missions associated with the space station. Detailed explanations of the reference missions for the BANTER project are given in Section 3.1.

The BANTER system is composed by two main propulsion systems sharing the propellant ammonia, namely the NTP and NEP system. Besides of these two main systems, other subsystems such as the propellant management system (PMS), PGS, and attitude control system (RCS) are included. The NEP systems consists of electric thrusters, for which mainly magnetoplasmadynamic thrusters (MPDT) are considered for the BANTER system. Fig. 1 shows the various subsystems of BANTER and their connections between each other. The NTP subsystem consists of an E-pump sending ammonia from its main propellant tank to the nuclear reactor coolant channels housed in the reactor core with nuclear fuel providing the energy to increase the temperature up to 3000 K. At the outlet of the coolant channels is an integrated convergent-divergent nozzle accelerating the hot exhausted gases and providing the thrust. A fundamental principle of the innovative nuclear reactor design is to achieve the ammonia decomposition into nitrogen and hydrogen within the reactor core before the acceleration in the nozzle. This reaction will halve the molecular weight of the exhaust gases [6] and increase the specific impulse to approximately 500 s. This exceeds the performance provided by chemical thrusters using cryogenic propellants, without the necessity to bring complex and voluminous tanks into orbit.

However, the BANTER system can also be operated driven by the NEP subsystem. During this phase, ammonia extracted from the main propellant tank and passed through the nuclear reactor changes its phase and absorbs heat from the reactor core. The gaseous ammonia expands in a turbine, converting work into electric power thanks to a generator connected to the turbine shaft. This power feeds then the E-pumps and electric thrusters of the NEP system. The electric thrusters, mainly MPDTs and arcjets are considered in the BANTER project, are fed with ammonia so that ammonia has as triple function: propellant for the thermonuclear component, propellant for the electric component, and working fluid for the PGS. From a mission analysis perspective, the overall transfer with the BANTER system can be divided into particular phases, during which either the NTP or the NEP subsystem are operated. One transfer phase is driven by the NTP system, offering high thrust and short transfer times but high propellant consumption due to its lower specific impulse, and one is driven by the NEP system, characterized by high specific impulse and reduced propellant consumption, but with longer transfer times resulting from its lower thrust level. These options are further discussed in Section 3. Detailed information about the BANTER project and its system requirements can be found in [6] and [7].

Fig. 1: BANTER system including subsystems and paths linking each other.

3. Methodology of Mission Analyses

One of the first objectives of BANTER is to define reference missions, in line with future plans of the European Space Agency (ESA) roadmaps, that fits the developed technologies. Although subsystems such as the nuclear space reactor, EPS, PGS, and PMS are being designed within the BANTER project up to a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 4, the baseline system requirements are derived from missions aligned with future ESA strategies, corresponding to a system with a TRL of 9. The reference missions considered for the BANTER system at TRL 9 are derived from the ISECG Exploration Roadmap 2024 [5], which projects the start of lunar surface exploration in 2030 and robotic sample return missions from Mars in 2040. Accordingly, the reference missions are defined as transfers to Moon or Mars, with BANTER offering the flexibility of either a single transfer or a space tug scenario, in which the spacecraft returns to Earth after delivering the payload to the target destination. Details about the mission parameters of the reference cases such as transfer time, departure and target orbit are given in Section 3.1.

The BANTER system enables the division of the overall transfer into distinct segments, depending on whether high thrust for impulsive manoeuvres or low thrust with high specific impulse for reduced propellant consumption is required. This flexibility highlights the potential advantages of hybrid propulsion architectures, as proposed in BANTER. A key question is whether hybrid manoeuvres provide measurable benefits compared to transfers relying solely on NTP or NEP systems. To address this, the mission analyses within the BANTER project examine not only hybrid propulsion scenarios but also reference cases employing purely NTP or purely NEP systems, thereby enabling a direct assessment of the relative benefits of the hybrid approach. Thus, the mission analyses are split into three parts:

For one, the total transfer to Moon or Mars is conducted with low-thrust spiralling manoeuvre relying on the BANTER system with purely NEP. In the first project phase, the mission requirements are calculated with analytical orbit equations for first estimations. A 2D model for the specification of the positions of the involved planets is assumed indicating that the departure, transfer and target orbits are positioned in the same plane and no inclination changes are required. It is intended to improve the calculation of mission requirements with convenient simulation tools after obtaining first results. The calculation of the required velocity increment Δv_{req} for a spiralling manoeuvre can be simply obtained with the difference of the spacecraft velocities at target $v_{i,end}$ and departure orbit $v_{i,start}$. The total velocity increment is given with the sum of the individual velocity increments Δv_i required for different spiralling manoeuvres. Furthermore, the spacecraft velocities at target and departure orbits can be derived from vis-

viva equation for circular orbits with the gravitational constant γ , the planet mass of the reference system M , and the orbit radius of target $r_{i,end}$ and departure orbit $r_{i,start}$ [8]:

$$\Delta v_{req} = \sum \Delta v_i \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta v_i = |v_{i,start} - v_{i,end}| \quad (2)$$

$$v_{i,start/end} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma M}{r_{i,start/end}}} \quad (3)$$

The required transfer time needs to be assumed for a spiralling manoeuvre since thruster parameters like thrust or propellant mass flow rate are required to be variable for first estimations. For the transfer option with a purely NEP system optimizing methods of the dimensionless Tsiolkovsky equation can be applied to obtain thruster parameters leading to optimal mission and system outcomes like minimum return transfer time for BANTER as a space tug or maximum payload mass fractions. Results for the analyses with a purely NEP system have already been obtained during the first phase of the BANTER project and are detailed described in this paper.

The second part of the mission analyses in the BANTER project are the one that describe an impulsive manoeuvre with a purely NTP system. Although these analyses are still pending, the impulsive manoeuvres are intended to be calculated using Hohmann transfer equations to determine the required velocity increment and transfer time [8].

The last part of the mission analyses is going to show the hybrid transfer with combined NTP and NEP. It is planned to investigate impulsive manoeuvres during the acceleration phase at the departure orbit and/or during the intersection phase at the target orbit, but to have a spiralling manoeuvre during the middle phase of the transfer. The required velocity increment can be estimated with the sum of the velocity increments for the spiralling $\Delta v_{i,spiralling}$ and impulsive manoeuvres $\Delta v_{i,impulsive}$:

$$\Delta v_{req} = \sum \Delta v_{i,spiralling} + \Delta v_{i,impulsive} \quad (4)$$

In the same way, the required transfer time τ_{req} is the sum of the transfer time for the spiralling $\tau_{i,spiralling}$ and the impulsive manoeuvres $\tau_{i,impulsive}$:

$$\tau_{req} = \sum \tau_{i,spiralling} + \tau_{i,impulsive} \quad (5)$$

By this, it is assessed how the transfer time reduces compared to the purely NEP manoeuvre according to higher thrust levels during the transfer beginning and end phase. And on the other hand, how the propellant consumption reduces compared to the purely NTP manoeuvre according to higher specific impulse levels during the transfer middle phase. For the comparison of all these three parts with each other a weighting function with different factors is required. The factors will include at least results of the transfer time, the payload mass fraction, and the propellant mass fraction for the three options. This weighting function is going to assess the importance of the different outcomes and requirements for BANTER's mission and system and will present a possibility how to compare advantages and disadvantages of the three transfer options with each other. Subsequent sections show the reference missions of the BANTER project and the methodology of the mission analyses with purely NEP in more detail.

3.1. Mission Cases

The mission cases of the BANTER project are in line with the exploration plans of the International Space Exploration Coordination Group (ISECG) [5]. Missions to Moon and Mars are foreseen for the BANTER system at TRL 9. Either single transfers to the target planet and a spacecraft disposal at the target planet or space tug transfers are assessed. The mission of the latter option starts with a transfer to the target planet, includes a payload delivering at the target planet and a return to the departure planet, in this case the Earth, at which the spacecraft will be disposed. The disposal phases are not included in the mission analyses so far but will be considered and investigated during the project.

For the mission analyses relevant orbit and transfer parameters are required. These are listed in Tab. 1 for the Moon mission and in Tab. 2 for the Mars mission, as well as some numbers for the purely NEP flight, that have been estimated or assumed for the BANTER project. Numbers for the required velocity increment are calculated with the

methods described in Section 3, but numbers for the required transfer time are assumed according to reasonable values and therefore a range of different transfer times are investigated.

3.2. Mission Analyses with Purely Nuclear-Electric Propulsion

The analyses for a purely NEP mission are based on analytical methods of rocket equation analyses for separately powered space propulsion, which is the case for EPSs. The so-called dimensionless Tsiolkovsky equation has been investigated and analysed by D.B. Langmuir recent years before [9] and can be used to optimize thruster parameters such as specific impulse, thrust efficiency or thrust for specific mission cases leading to optimal results in terms of payload mass fractions, required velocity increments, and transfer times.

D.B. Langmuir found out that for EPS not the highest achievable specific impulse is automatically the optimal solution in terms of highest achievable payload mass.

Tab. 1: Orbit and transfer parameters for the BANTER system with purely NEP and the mission to Moon.

MISSION TO MOON	
Departure orbit	NSO: circular orbit with 900 km altitude around Earth
Target orbit	Low Lunar Orbit (LLO): circular orbit with 100 km altitude around Moon
Transfer properties	Direct flight (in this case: spiralling manoeuvres)
Transfer options & estimated mission parameters	Single transfer: $\Delta v_{req} \approx 6.386$ km/s $\tau_{req} \approx 90-250$ d
	Space tug with return to Earth: $\Delta v_{req} \approx 12.772$ km/s $\tau_{req} \approx 200-350$ d

Tab. 2: Orbit and transfer parameters for the BANTER system with purely NEP and the mission to Mars.

MISSION TO MARS	
Departure orbit	NSO: circular orbit with 900 km altitude around Earth
Target orbit	Low Martian Orbit (LMO): circular orbit with 250 km altitude around Mars
Transfer properties	Direct flight (in this case: spiralling manoeuvres), refuelling stop at Moon orbit may be considered for future investigations
Transfer options & estimated mission parameters	Single transfer: $\Delta v_{req} \approx 10.14$ km/s $\tau_{req} \approx 200-300$ d
	Space tug with return to Earth: $\Delta v_{req} \approx 20.28$ km/s $\tau_{req} \approx 350-450$ d

Of course, higher specific impulses lead to reduced propellant consumptions, but to achieve higher specific impulse levels the masses of the spacecraft powertrain, required for the supply of electrical power for the EPS, increases as well. This leads to the effect, that for a particular mission with known mission parameters (Δv_{req} and τ_{req}) an optimal specific impulse exists leading to the highest possible payload mass fraction. Detailed information about the derivation of the dimensionless Tsiolkovsky equation and useful addendums can be found in [9], [10] and [11].

Fig. 2: Code configuration for mission analyses with purely NEP with a single transfer.

3.2.1 Methodology for a Single Transfer to the Target Planet

However, the equations of D.B. Langmuir can directly be applied to the BANTER system with purely NEP only for the transfer option of a single transfer. For these analyses an analytical code within MathWorks programming environment MATLAB is developed and adapted for the needs of the BANTER project. Fig. 2 shows the code configuration for these analyses including the applied equations of D.B. Langmuir [9].

Since analytical methods are applied for initial mission and spacecraft estimations – where many parameters remain unknown – several code inputs are treated as variable in the early stages. A key aspect is the option to either define the transfer time as a variable within a predefined range, while fixing values for the EPS's thrust efficiency, or to fix the transfer time (within that range) and treat thrust efficiency as a variable instead. The analyses then yield either a 3D plot of payload-structure mass fraction versus specific impulse and transfer time, or a 3D plot of payload-structure mass fraction versus specific impulse and thrust efficiency. This choice between variable transfer time and variable thrust efficiency is necessary because the system of governing equations for payload mass fraction is underdetermined, and introducing additional variables would prevent an analytical solution. Another variable input for the mission analyses within the BANTER project belongs to the available electrical power level provided by the nuclear reactor and the PGS for the electric thrusters. Since this number is not determined yet, a minimum power level of 30 kW and a maximum power level of 200 kW are investigated. For the analytical estimation of the payload-structure mass fraction μ_{pls} the introduction of the energy characteristic velocity v_c is important. It can be derived from system parameters, i.e. thrust efficiency η_T , available electrical power for EPS P_{el} , mass of powertrain m_{PS} , and mission parameters, i.e. transfer time τ :

$$v_c = \sqrt{2\eta_T \cdot \frac{P_{el}}{m_{PS}} \cdot \tau}. \quad (6)$$

Eqn. 6 directly illustrates why transfer time and thrust efficiency cannot both be treated as variables. The payload-structure mass fraction, which is basically the payload and structure mass divided by the total spacecraft mass, can be derived from D.B. Langmuir's dimensionless Tsiolkovsky equation and the variable specific impulse I_{sp} multiplied with the gravitational acceleration g_0 :

$$\mu_{pls} = \left(\frac{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}{v_c}\right)^2 \left(e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} - 1\right) + e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}. \quad (7)$$

The total spacecraft mass also includes the mass of the powertrain and the propellant mass. For the comparison of the consequences for different specific impulse levels, it is also important to calculate the mass fractions of these subsystems (propellant mass fraction μ_{prop} and powertrain mass fraction μ_{PS}) with its masses divided by the total

spacecraft mass. By this, the result plots can directly show the mass distribution of the BANTER system according to the specific impulse of the EPS:

$$\mu_{prop} = 1 - \frac{1}{e^{\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} \quad (8)$$

$$\mu_{PS} = 1 - \mu_{prop} - \mu_{pls} \quad (9)$$

With mission parameters that are estimated with Eqn. 1-3 3D and 2D plots of the payload-structure mass fraction and detailed thruster and mission parameter numbers for a maximum payload-structure mass fraction or 80% of the maximum value can be derived. These parameters are specific impulse, thrust, thrust efficiency, and transfer time. In the end, the thrust F of the EPS can be derived from known thruster parameters (found with the optimal solution for the payload-structure mass fraction):

$$F = \frac{2\eta_T \cdot P_{el}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0} \quad (10)$$

3.2.2 Methodology for Space Tug Missions with Return to Departure Planet

The analytical model for space tug missions to the Moon and Mars differs from that of a single transfer, as the payload and structural mass of the spacecraft cannot be combined into a single payload-structure mass fraction. In BANTER's space tug missions, the payload is delivered exclusively to the target planet, whereas only the structural, powertrain and propellant mass contributes to the spacecraft mass on the return transfer to Earth. Consequently, the analytical equations derived by D.B. Langmuir required adaption to account for the space tug mission profile, as also described in [10]. Fig. 3 shows again the code configuration for the space tug mission analyses with the adapted and extended equations of D.B. Langmuir. The input parameters for the space tug analyses remain the same as for a single transfer, with the exception that the structural mass fraction is fixed at 0.2, a value commonly cited in the literature as a representative estimate for spacecraft structural mass fractions [12]. The energy characteristic velocity is calculated in the same way then mentioned in Section 3.2.1, that means that Eqn. 6 remains the same. The only difference for space tugs is, that the transfer time is separated into two parts: the outbound flight time to the target destination τ_1 and the return flight time back to Earth τ_2 . For calculating the energy characteristic velocity with Eqn. 6, the correct transfer time τ_1 or τ_2 needs to be used depending on which transfer section is considered. However, Eqn. 7 changes to the following if

Fig. 3: Code configuration for mission analyses with purely NEP with a space tug transfer.

space tugs are considered with a fixed structure mass fraction μ_S of 0.2 (spacecraft structure mass divided by the total spacecraft mass):

$$\mu_{pl} = e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} - \left(\frac{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}{v_c} \right)^2 \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}}{e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} - \frac{\mu_S}{e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} \quad (11)$$

Hereby, the payload mass fraction μ_{pl} can be defined as the payload mass divided by the total spacecraft mass. In the same way, the propellant mass fraction is calculated in a different way, since it is necessary to take into account that the payload mass is delivered at the target destination and not taken back to Earth:

$$\mu_{prop} = 1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} + \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}}{e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} \cdot \left(\frac{(I_{sp} \cdot g_0)^2 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} \right)}{2\tau_1 \cdot \eta_T \cdot \frac{P_{el}}{m_{PS}}} + \mu_S \right) \quad (12)$$

Additionally, the mass fraction for the powertrain needs to consider the structure mass fraction, so Eqn. 9 changes to the following:

$$\mu_{PS} = 1 - \mu_{prop} - \mu_{pl} - \mu_S \quad (13)$$

With the described equations it is also possible for space tug missions to plot the transfer time of the return flight over the specific impulse and thrust efficiency or transfer time of the outbound flight. This is shown with Eqn. 14 and can be used to find an optimal specific impulse for a minimal return flight time:

$$\tau_2 = \frac{\frac{(I_{sp} \cdot g_0)^2 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} \right) + \mu_S \cdot \tau_1}{2\eta_T \cdot \frac{P_{el}}{m_{PS}}}}{e^{-\frac{\Delta v_{req}}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} \quad (14)$$

4. Results

The dimensionless Tsiolkovsky analyses, described in Section 3, can be applied to optimize the payload mass fraction, velocity increment budget, or transfer time. This approach is used to derive system parameters such as the required specific impulse, thrust efficiency, and thrust level, as well as mission parameters such as the transfer time needed to reach the optimum point.

Tab. 3: List of variable inputs for BANTER NEP mission analyses including the selectable options.

INPUT PARAMETER	OPTIONS
Target planet	* Moon: LLO * Mars: LMO
Transfer option	* Single transfer * Space tug with return to Earth
Electrical input power	* 30 kW * 200 kW
2 nd variable parameter ¹	* Thrust efficiency η_T * Transfer time of outbound flight τ_1

¹ specific impulse is the first variable parameter for the analyses

Fig. 4: Payload-structure mass fraction over specific impulse and thrust efficiency of a single transfer to Moon with an available electrical power of 200 kW and a transfer time of 90 days.

Within the BANTER project, the focus is on optimizing the payload mass fraction of the total system, as this is directly linked to a reduced propellant mass fraction and highlights the advantage of NEP over NTP. Since many parameters are initially treated as variables, the analyses can yield a range of different outputs.

Tab. 3 provides an overview of the variable inputs for the BANTER NEP mission analyses and the selectable options, while the following list outlines the possible outputs:

- * Output of detailed parameter values in table form
 - ♦ Maximum payload mass fraction and corresponding specific impulse, thrust efficiency, thrust, and required transfer time to achieve this value
 - ♦ 80% of maximum payload mass fraction and corresponding specific impulse, thrust efficiency, thrust, and required transfer time to achieve this value
- * Graphic file output showing achievable mass fractions (of payload, structure, powertrain, and propellant)
 - ♦ 3D plot with payload mass fraction over specific impulse, and thrust efficiency or transfer time of outbound flight
 - ♦ 2D plot with mass fractions over specific impulse for variable thrust efficiency or transfer time of outbound flight
- * Graphic file output (2D plot) showing transfer time of return flight over specific impulse for variable thrust efficiency or transfer time of outbound flight

These outputs are generated for each mission case, whether a single transfer or a space tug transfer, and for each input configuration. Sections 4.1 to 4.4 summarize the results for the respective mission cases, illustrating the different output options and providing an overview of the range of outcomes that can be obtained with the analyses.

4.1. Mission to Moon with a Single Transfer

The single transfer to the Moon analysed within the BANTER project requires a total velocity increment of approximately 6.4 km/s, with transfer times between 90 and 250 days investigated. Fig. 4 presents a 3D plot of the payload-structure mass fraction as a function of specific impulse and thrust efficiency for a 90-day transfer, assuming a maximum electrical power of 200 kW provided by the nuclear reactor.

Solid black lines denote cross-sections at constant thrust efficiencies, illustrating the dependency of the payload-structure mass fraction on thrust efficiency. The red line highlights the maximum achievable payload-structure mass

fractions, indicating the corresponding specific impulse and thrust efficiency. For transfers with the minimum reactor power level, reasonable payload-structure mass fractions (defined here as values >0.2 , based on the assumed structural mass fraction of spacecraft from literature [12]) are only obtained for transfer times of at least 250 days and thrust efficiencies above 50%. Tab. 4 summarizes this case, providing maximum payload-structure mass fractions for thrust efficiencies between 20% and 80%, along with the corresponding specific impulses and thrust levels.

Tab. 4: Maximum payload-structure mass fractions with required EPS parameters for a 250-day single transfer to Moon with an electrical power of 30 kW.

$\mu_{pls} / -$	I_{sp} / s	$\eta_T / -$	F / N
0.005917	428.2	0.2	2.857
0.1028	641.8	0.3	2.859
0.1786	802.0	0.4	3.051
0.2381	948.8	0.5	3.223
0.2859	1069	0.6	3.433
0.3255	1189	0.7	3.600
0.3589	1296	0.8	3.776

At minimum power and 250-day transfer time, a maximum payload-structure mass fraction of 0.36 is achieved at 80% thrust efficiency, corresponding to a specific impulse of ~ 1296 s and thrust of ~ 3.8 N. At higher power levels (in this case 200 kW), the attainable payload-structure mass fraction increases, with higher corresponding specific impulses and thrust levels. Tab. 5 details these results for a 250-day transfer at various thrust efficiencies.

Tab. 5: Maximum payload-structure mass fractions with required EPS parameters for a 250-day single transfer to Moon with an electrical power of 200 kW.

$\mu_{pls} / -$	I_{sp} / s	$\eta_T / -$	F / N
0.4775	1777	0.2	4.590
0.5599	2257	0.3	5.419
0.6119	2658	0.4	6.137
0.6485	3018	0.5	6.755
0.6762	3338	0.6	7.328
0.6982	3632	0.7	7.858
0.7161	3912	0.8	8.337

With increased power, shorter transfer times also become feasible: for example, with 200 kW reactor power and a thrust efficiency of 50%, a payload-structure mass fraction of 0.45 can be achieved for a 90-day Moon transfer if the thrusters provide a specific impulse of ~ 1670 s and a thrust of ~ 12 N.

4.2. Space Tug Mission to Moon with Return to Earth

The space tug transfer to the Moon requires a total velocity increment of 12.8 km/s and cumulative transfer times of 200-350 days. Analyses with a minimum electrical power of 30 kW available for the EPS indicate that this power level is insufficient to yield reasonable payload mass fractions under a 250-day outbound transfer constraint. Even at the highest realistic thrust efficiency of 80%, the resulting payload mass fractions are negative, indicating the mission infeasible under these conditions. Further analyses show that viable results can only be achieved by extending the outbound transfer time to 475 days combined with a thrust efficiency of at least 70% at 30 kW, or alternatively by increasing the reactor power to 60 kW while maintaining a minimum thrust efficiency of 70% for a 250-day transfer to the Moon. Without such adjustments in power or outbound transfer time, a lunar space tug mission with the BANTER system cannot be realized given the elevated mission requirements.

At higher power levels – specifically the maximum of 200 kW – reasonable payload mass fractions are attainable for outbound transfer times of 180 days or more, largely independent of thrust efficiency. This behaviour is shown in Fig. 5, which illustrates the mass fraction distribution of the spacecraft for a 180-day outbound transfer at 200 kW over specific impulse for various thrust efficiencies. Solid coloured lines represent payload mass fractions across different thrust efficiencies and specific impulse levels, while the solid black line marks the fixed structure mass

fraction of 0.2. Dashed coloured lines show the decreasing propellant mass fraction with rising specific impulse, reflecting the reduced propellant demand with higher specific impulses. Conversely, dotted coloured lines indicate the increasing powertrain mass fraction with higher specific impulses, consistent with the greater importance of the powertrain subsystem for increased system requirements. The sum of the structure, payload, propellant, and powertrain mass fractions equals 1 for each thrust efficiency case and a particular specific impulse level. These plots clearly describe the specific impulse ranges associated with high payload mass fractions and their relation to the spacecraft's overall mass budget.

Tab. 6 summarizes the dependency of outbound transfer time on payload mass fraction at a thrust efficiency of 80%.

Tab. 6: Maximum payload mass fractions with required EPS parameters and outbound flight times for a space tug transfer to Moon with an electrical power of 200 kW and an 80% thrust efficiency.

$\mu_{pl} / -$	I_{sp} / s	τ_1 / d	F / N
0.01747	1903	50	17.14
0.2241	2604	90	12.53
0.3571	3405	150	9.579
0.4177	3946	200	8.267
0.4587	4447	250	7.336
0.4889	4887	300	6.675

Fig. 5: Mass fractions over specific impulse and thrust efficiency of a space tug transfer to Moon with an available electrical power of 200 kW and an outbound transfer time of 180 days.

It lists the maximum achievable payload mass fractions for varying transfer durations along with the corresponding thruster parameters. For example, a payload mass fraction of 0.22 can be achieved for a 90-day outbound flight if the thruster provides a specific impulse of ~2604 s and a thrust of ~12.5 N.

Fig. 6: Spacecraft mass fractions over specific impulse and thrust efficiency of a single transfer to Mars with an available electrical power of 30 kW and a transfer time of 250 days.

4.3. Mission to Mars with a Single Transfer

The single transfer to Mars analysed within the BANTER project requires a total velocity increment of ~ 10 km/s, with transfer times between 200 and 300 days investigated. At the minimum power level of 30 kW, viable results are obtained only for transfer times of at least 250 days and at the highest realistic thrust efficiency of 80%. As shown in Fig. 6, which plots the payload-structure mass fraction along with propellant and powertrain fractions over specific impulse for different thrust efficiencies, even this configuration yields a maximum payload-structure mass fraction of only 0.12.

Tab. 7: Maximum payload-structure mass fractions with required EPS parameters for a 250-day single transfer to Mars with an electrical power of 200 kW.

μ_{pls} / -	I_{sp} / s	η_T / -	F / N
0.2527	1563	0.2	5.218
0.3566	2057	0.3	5.947
0.4255	2457	0.4	6.637
0.4755	2818	0.5	7.235
0.5140	3138	0.6	7.796
0.5448	3432	0.7	8.317
0.5703	3712	0.8	8.787

Assuming a structure mass fraction of 0.2, this would imply a negative payload mass, which is physically unrealistic. Therefore, further analyses were conducted for the Mars single transfer under relaxed power and time constraints. Results indicate that realistic payload-structure mass fractions can be achieved either by extending the transfer time to 400 days at 30 kW with a minimum thrust efficiency of 70%, or by increasing the available reactor power to 50 kW while keeping the original time constraint. At the maximum available power level of 200 kW, reasonable results are obtained even for short transfer durations.

A transfer time of 90 days yields acceptable payload-structure mass fractions, while at 250 days efficiencies as low as 20% still achieve values above 0.2. Tab. 7 summarizes these results, providing maximum payload-structure mass fractions for different thrust efficiencies along with their corresponding thruster parameters. Under optimal

conditions, a maximum payload-structure mass fraction of ~ 0.57 is achieved with a thrust efficiency of 80%, a specific impulse of ~ 3712 s, and a thrust of ~ 8.8 N.

4.4. Space Tug Mission to Mars with Return to Earth

The space tug transfer to Mars requires a total velocity increment of approximately 20 km/s, with total flight times of 350-450 days investigated. Similar to the lunar space tug case, the minimum available power of 30 kW proves insufficient to achieve viable payload mass fractions, as none of the tested configurations result in positive payload capacity. Under the combined constraints of 30 kW power and a 300-day outbound transfer, no feasible solutions exist. Further analyses were therefore performed to determine the power and time requirements for positive payload mass fractions. Results show that with only 30 kW, achieving feasibility would require extending the outbound transfer time to ~ 1100 days at a maximum realistic thrust efficiency of 80%.

Fig. 7: Mass fractions over specific impulse and outbound flight times of a space tug transfer to Mars with an available electrical power of 200 kW and a thrust efficiency of 80%.

Such a scenario is considered unrealistic, since the nuclear reactor cannot be expected to provide a continuous output of 30 kW over this duration and the mission takes too long to be comparable with NTP analyses. Alternatively, increasing the available power to at least 140 kW enables positive payload mass fractions for a 250-day outbound transfer, again assuming a thrust efficiency of 80%.

At the maximum reactor output of 200 kW, significantly improved payload fractions are obtained, though at the cost of higher specific impulse requirements. Tab. 8 presents the detailed payload mass fractions and corresponding thruster parameters for a 250-day outbound transfer, while Fig. 7 shows the distribution of mass fractions (payload, structure, propellant, and powertrain) for different transfer times at 80% thrust efficiency. The maximum payload mass fraction at each transfer time is indicated by a cross. These results demonstrate that outbound transfers shorter than 150 days do not yield positive payload mass fractions, even at 80% efficiency.

Overall, the analyses confirm that a Mars tug mission is feasible at 200 kW, achieving a maximum payload mass fraction of ~ 0.25 with 80% thrust efficiency, a specific impulse of ~ 4347 s, a thrust level of ~ 7.5 N, and a 250-day outbound transfer. Fig. 8 further illustrates the dependency between return flight time and specific impulse for different outbound transfer times. An optimum specific impulse range of 2000-2500 s minimizes return flight times, whereas longer outbound transfers require proportionally longer return transfers.

Tab. 8: Maximum payload mass fractions with required EPS parameters for a space tug transfer to Mars with an electrical power of 200 kW and an outbound flight time of 250 days.

$\mu_{pl} / -$	I_{sp} / s	$\eta_T / -$	F / N
0.01361	3025	0.4	5.392
0.1006	3385	0.5	6.022
0.1640	3746	0.6	6.531
0.2128	4046	0.7	7.054
0.2520	4347	0.8	7.504

This effect is directly linked to thruster operation: longer transfer times allow for higher specific impulses and reduced thrust levels, which increase payload fractions but inevitably increase the return transfer time as well.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This paper presents an overview of the first-phase mission analyses of the BANTER project, focusing on results for purely NEP transfers. BANTER is an European Union funded initiative aimed at developing a bimodal propulsion system using ammonia as the sole propellant – serving both the NTP and EPS, as well as the working fluid for the PGS.

The paper introduces the BANTER system architecture, comprising the nuclear reactor with an integrated thermal nozzle for NTP, the PGS for converting thermal energy into electrical power, and the EPS consisting of electric thrusters.

Fig. 8: Return flight time over specific impulse and outbound flight times of a space tug transfer to Mars with an available electrical power of 200 kW and a thrust efficiency of 80 %.

Mission analyses play a central role in assessing the potential of the BANTER system at TRL 9, especially considering the advantages of ammonia as a propellant. Ammonia is a candidate for in-situ resource utilization on the Moon and Mars, offering the potential to reduce launch propellant requirements and enable local refuelling for return flights.

Within this first phase, both single transfers to the Moon and Mars, as well as space tug missions returning to Earth, were examined. The analyses employed dimensionless Tsiolkovsky methods (after D.B. Langmuir [9]),

extended to model space tug operations and subsystem mass dependencies. A dedicated analytical tool was implemented in MATLAB to optimize payload mass fractions and derive thruster requirements, as well as to assess overall mission feasibility under specific system and mission constraints. These constraints included available reactor power, thruster efficiency, and mission transfer time.

Results indicate that space tug missions are only feasible if the minimum power levels are raised – at least to 60 kW for lunar transfers and 140 kW for Mars transfers – assuming reasonable transfer durations. Conversely, single transfers to the Moon can achieve payload-structure mass fractions above 0.25 with only 30 kW at 60% thruster efficiency. At higher reactor outputs (up to 200 kW), all mission cases – single transfers and space tug missions alike – yield viable and in many cases highly favourable payload and payload-structure mass fractions.

Future phases of the BANTER project will extend these analyses to purely NTP-driven transfers, which offer higher thrust levels but lower specific impulse compared to NEP. The increased propellant mass requirements in NTP missions will be critical for comparison. Ultimately, the project will investigate hybrid propulsion scenarios, where the NTP system provides high-acceleration manoeuvres and the NEP system operates during low-thrust phases. A weighted comparison function – including mission time, payload mass fraction, and propellant mass fraction – will be developed to identify the propulsion architecture delivering optimal performance across mission and system parameters.

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